

Dabble Games as a Media to Improve Listening Skills for Elementary School Students

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Abstract

This study aims to explore the effectiveness of dabble games as a medium for improving the listening skills of elementary school students. Experimental research methods are used to collect data from students involved in dabble game activities. The results of the research show a significant improvement in student listening abilities after participating in these games. These findings show that Dabble can be an effective tool in improving elementary-school students' listening ability and make a positive contribution to their language learning. The practical implications of this study provide new insights into the development of interesting and interactive learning methods to improve listening skill at the elementary education level.

Keywords: Dabble Games, Listening Skills, SDN Konang 04 Pamekasan

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Introduction

The objective of the teaching and learning process is to effectively cultivate and enhance the students' potential (Yulianti & Sulistiyawati, 2020). The occurrence of a learning process is accompanied by a simultaneous teaching process. This concept is presumably straightforward to comprehend, as it follows that if an individual is leaning, it is evident that someone is instructing them, and conversely, if someone is teaching, there must be someone who is leaning. Teaching and learning is an interactive process between educators and students, in which these activities possess educational significance with the goal of fostering and enhancing students' potential (Parinussa et al., 2023). Hence, instructors are anticipated to possess the ability to create inventive learning experiences for their students. English is widely used as a means of communication at significant international gatherings by individuals from diverse nations. (Rao, 2019). Proficiency in English is crucial due to its widespread usage as a global medium for accessing diverse sources of information across various domains of life (Isnaini & Aminatun, 2021). English holds significant importance in various domains. Additionally, it serves as a global language and is the primary language in numerous countries worldwide. In order to achieve that, it is necessary to acquire and proficiently command the English language. Mastering English offers numerous advantages,

such as facilitating international business transactions and enabling comprehension of English-language product labels and compositions. Additionally, proficiency in English allows effective communication with foreigners and comprehension of their speech. There are numerous advantages that can be gained by achieving proficiency in English.

Teaching is providing guidance and education to a student with the aim of enabling them to gain knowledge and develop skills (Shin & Hickey, 2021). Teaching is the act of imparting lessons or knowledge to students or individuals, enabling them to achieve mastery in a specific subject or area of knowledge (Srivastava & Agnihotri, 2022). Education can be imparted in any location and at any moment (Gandhi, 2021). During the teaching process, it is advantageous to impart one's abilities and expertise to effectively address current challenges. Typically, this instruction is facilitated by an educator (Schabas, 2023).

Learning is the deliberate and systematic endeavor undertaken by humans to acquire and cultivate skills, attitudes, and talents (Jaiswal & Al-Hattami, 2020). Learning is the conscious endeavor undertaken by an individual to expand their knowledge (Eschenbacher & Fleming, 2020), hence enhancing their personal potential and facilitating changes in attitudes and abilities. Education can take place in any location and at any time, without limitations. Learning offers advantages to individuals seeking knowledge, specifically by providing new insights and increasing awareness.

Teachers have access to several learning tools to effectively manage the classroom, one of which is game-based learning (Hartt et al., 2020). Media playback is a crucial component of the educational setting as it has the potential to augment impactful learning experiences, uplift mood, and optimize learning outcomes (Hawes & Arya, 2023). One effective strategy that teachers might employ is game-based learning (Liu et al., 2020), as it has the potential to enhance students' engagement and prevent boredom. Particularly in the current period, kids are likely to be captivated by the incorporation of games into the learning process. From my perspective, incorporating educational games that align with the curriculum can generate student interest and make the learning process enjoyable. Consequently, students' retention and motivation levels will be significantly elevated (Pedler et al., 2022). The game "Dabble" involves creating words from letter chips (Hall et al., 2020). Subsequently, students will watch a video or listen to a song. Afterwards, they will be provided with random letters and instructed to compose two words based on what they heard in the movie or music.

Several studies have shown the effectiveness of using games in improving listening skills. A study conducted by El-Sayed, Qoura, and Abdel-Fattah (Syafii et al., 2020) discovered that the utilization of games, such as Tic Tac Toe Game and Running Dictation

Game, can effectively improve students' listening abilities. The study proposes that incorporating enjoyable activities, such as games, can serve as an alternate approach to improve kids' listening abilities. Another study (Hwang et al., 2016), assessed auditory comprehension and oral communication abilities within a mobile game-oriented educational setting featuring realistic scenarios. The findings indicated that students in the experimental group, who utilized a mobile system for educational tasks, demonstrated a considerably higher level of achievement in the verbal post-test compared to the students in the control group. Nevertheless, the performance of both groups was identical on the listening post-test. According to the study, the utilization of game-based learning activities, when facilitated by a mobile system, can greatly enhance students' speaking abilities. A study by Sejdiu (Sejdiu, 2017), examined the progress of listening comprehension in students who utilized multimedia technology in comparison to those who did not. The study revealed that pupils demonstrated enhanced information retention when provided with both verbal and visual help. While the study did not expressly employ the Dabble game, it showcases the capacity of multimedia technology to augment listening abilities.

Based on these findings, it appears that the incorporation of games and other forms of multimedia technology into educational settings has the potential to be an effective means of improving listening ability. Despite the fact that the Dabble game was not particularly included in this research, there is a universal consensus that engaging children in activities that are both entertaining and participatory can successfully improve their listening abilities.

The objective of this study is to enhance students' proficiency in English listening. Additionally, this research aims to demonstrate that rural schools are capable of achieving proficiency in English, particularly in listening skills. Furthermore, it seeks to dispel the notion that English is an exceedingly challenging subject for elementary school students to grasp.

Research Method

In a study there must be a research method that will be used, the researcher chooses a qualitative research method. According to Moleong (2017) qualitative research is research that intends to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by research subjects such as behavior, perception, motivation, action and others holistically and by means of constructions in the form of words and language, in a special natural context by utilizing

various methods natural. So qualitative research is research that aims to understand the phenomena or problems that occur in SDN Konang 04 schools, what difficulties are experienced by students and also what actions can be taken so that problems can be resolved.

SDN Konang 04 is one of the elementary schools in the Galis sub-district which has 6 classrooms ranging from grade 1 to grade 6. However, the scope of the class to be studied is grade 6. The researcher chose this class because many students experience difficulties in learning language English and assume that English is difficult to learn and understand, so the researcher aims to apply the learning method, namely the Dabble game to overcome the problems experienced by students and with this Dabble game, it can make learning more interesting. So that students are more enthusiastic and do not think English lessons are difficult. Here the researcher uses the game as a learning tool which will require several letters to be made and randomly distributed to students to play the Dabble game. And here the researcher will focus on the Dabble game learning method on students' listening skills.

Data obtained by conducting interviews and surveys of what conditions are like in the field. The instrument in this study uses tests on students about what the researcher examines, such as observing how students behave during the teaching and learning process, what are the students' difficulties in learning especially English and after that giving.

Because what will be studied is grade 6 where the atmosphere and conditions of grade 6 are less conducive, lack enthusiasm for learning, and really don't like English lessons where according to them English lessons are very difficult to understand. However, when the English subject matter is wrapped in games, they are very enthusiastic and easy to understand the material and vice versa if the. Material is very lacking, sometimes speaking for themselves. So that extra energy is needed to manage the class so that it is conducive and also so that the desired desires or goals can be achieved. tests to students to measure the extent of students' abilities.

To obtain accurate and accountable data for the research under study, that's where the researcher used a data collection technique consisting of:

1. Observation is a data collection technique by observing and recording. Where the researcher observes what the deficiencies are and how the development of the object under study is based on the reality and facts that exist in the field or school under study. Where the researcher directly reviewed the class in order to find out the students' listening and vocabulary.

2. An interview is a conversation between two or more people and takes place between the source and the interviewer. In this case the researcher directly interviewed the school principal to find out what the condition of the school was like and also with the English teacher to find out what the students' English proficiency was like.
3. Documentation is a record of events that occurred in the past. Where this documentation is in the form of writing or pictures and here the researcher takes documentation related to the results of his research in the field or school.in English lessons.

Data collection is the process of collecting, measuring and analyzing various types of information using standardized techniques. In collecting data, researchers used 3 techniques in the research conducted, namely observation, interview and documentation.

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Documentation is a record of events that occurred in the past. Where this documentation is in the form of writing or pictures and here the researcher takes documentation related to the results of his research in the field or school.

Researcher conducted data analysis when the teaching and learning process was completed. This data analysis was carried out to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the teaching and learning process in schools, cohesiveness in using learning tools or media, and various problems that exist in the teaching and learning process inside and outside the classroom. And with this observation or research it is hoped that we can revise any existing problems in the teaching and learning process so that we can find solutions to each existing problem and also with this evaluation can improve the implementation of learning or teaching and learning processes. In other words, where any deficiencies from the results of this observation can be used to determine how the learning or teaching and learning process is the next day and with this evaluation, learning will be even better than the previous day.

Finding and Discussion

Dabble game is one of the learning media through games that can be used by anyone because of the easy way to do it. This game is a word order game in general so that students will easily understand how to play the Dabble game.

How to apply the Dabble game carried out by researchers in improving listening skills in English learning, namely:

1. The first step is to explain how to play the Dabble game
2. After explaining how to play it, the research started playing the song “We love Allah”.
3. After the song is finished, students are asked to arrange or arrange the letters that have been given to form an English word according to the song we love Allah.

Here the researcher instructs students to listen and watch the video for the song “we love Allah”. Because the students whose English skills were studied were lacking, especially their listening skills, researchers used video instead of audio to adjust to the abilities of the students in the class being studied. After the implementation is complete, the researcher will explain the research results obtained and accompanied by a discussion to improve listening skills in English learning.

No	Name	Response		
		Accepted	Middle	Unaccepted
1.	Zulfa Safitri			✓
2.	Mohammad Alfian Affandi		✓	
3.	Dina Azsura Wiyanti	✓		
4.	Aulia Unzila Putri	✓		
5.	Jelita Mahsa Zataarifa	✓		
6.	Devi Purnamayanti	✓		
7.	David Sbastian Ramadhani		✓	
8.	Soffan Sofyan		✓	

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that out of the eight students, there was one student who did not understand how to play the Dabble game. And 3 students are in the middle between understanding and a little not understanding how to play Dabble games that are adapted to learning English. While the other 4 students really understood very well how to play the Dabble game.

Based on the results of research that has been carried out by researchers, it can be concluded that in fact using game based learning, namely Dabble games to improve listening skills in English learning. The following are algorithm students regarding the application of Dabble games in learning, namely:

NO	NAME	Student's Statements		
		Accepted	Middle	Unaccepted
1.	Zulfa Safitri			✓
2.	Mohammad Alfian Affandi		✓	
3.	Dina Azsura Wiyanti	✓		
4.	Aulia Unzila Putri	✓		
5.	Dina Azsura Wiyanti	✓		
6.	Devi Purnamayanti	✓		
7.	David Sbastian Ramadhani		✓	
8.	Soffan Sofyan		✓	

Based on the table above, we can see that 1 student said it was difficult to use the Dabble game media. 3 students are in the middle, where the 3 people say it is not too easy and not too difficult if learning is applied using learning media such as this Dabble game. And 4 students find it very easy if learning is wrapped in game-based learning such as the Dabble game

Based on research conducted by researchers in the context of implementing Dabble Game to improve listening skills in learning English for Konang 04 Elementary School students, there was one student when implementing this Dabble game having difficulty finding or looking for letters and also difficulty in arranging letters according to displayed videos. The researcher provided the video for the song "We love Allah" because this student's ability in English lessons was very lacking and also when watching the video, the student was less focused so it was difficult to arrange and find the letters he wanted. arrange because these students do not know what words to arrange, and how to arrange the correct letters according to the video being watched.

NO	NAME	Student Response			Reason
		Accepted	Middle	Unaccepted	
1.	Zulfa Safitri		✓		Don't understand how to play because don't listen to explanations

			properly and don't have enough knowledge of English
2.	Mohammad Alfan Affandi	✓	Understand how to play, but due to lack of knowledge about English vocabulary, putting words together becomes a bit difficult. And the difficulty in finding letters is due to not knowing the correct sequence of letters as seen and heard in the video
3.	Dina Azsura Wiyanti	✓	Understand well in every step of playing dabble game due to good listening and good knowledge of English. Difficulty when looking for letters to be assembled due to rush and feeling panicked.
4.	Aulia Unzila Putri	✓	Understand well in every step of playing dabble game due to good listening and good knowledge of English
5.	Dina Azsura Wiyanti	✓	Understand well in every step of playing dabble game due to good listening and good knowledge of English. Difficulty when looking for letters to be assembled due to rush and feeling panicked.
6.	Devi Purnamayanti	✓	Understand well in every step of playing dabble game due to good listening and good knowledge of English. Difficulty when looking for letters to be assembled due to rush and feeling panicked.
7.	David Sbastian Ramadhani	✓	Understand how to play, but due to lack of knowledge about English vocabulary, putting words together becomes a bit difficult. And the difficulty in finding letters is due to not knowing the correct sequence of letters as seen and heard in the video
8.	Soffan Sofyan	✓	Understand how to play, but due to lack of knowledge about English

vocabulary, putting words together becomes a bit difficult. And the difficulty in finding letters is due to not knowing the correct sequence of letters as seen and heard in the video

Here I use a video where students not only listen to the song but also watch the video of the song because they see the ability of students who are still lacking. So researchers use video. From the table above, we can see that out of 8 students, there was one student who did not understand at all, 3 students understood but when it was applied, they had difficulty when stringing words together, and there were also those who had no problems at all when playing the Dabble game involving students' listening skills. One student could not understand at all because his thinking skills were slow and his knowledge of English was lacking. 3 other people understand but have difficulty when arranging letters according to the English words found in the video due to a lack of knowledge of English, especially in the students' English vocabulary. The other 4 understood it the way it was, however, 3 of them had difficulty finding letters because they were too hasty and also panicked so they lost focus which resulted in difficulty finding the letters they wanted. Meanwhile, one student had no problems because his English skills were very good and he was also very calm when looking for the letter he wanted so he didn't lose focus.

When applying the Dabble game to improve listening skills, you need to focus on watching videos so you know what words to look for and how to arrange the words correctly. In addition, in finding the letters we want to arrange, we must not be in a hurry and panic which will result in less focus on finding the letters we want to arrange. So calm is also needed because it will really help to focus more.

The impact of Dabble games in English learning to improve listening skills
Based on the results of research conducted on the impact of Dabble games to improve listening skills in learning English, that is, almost all students said that by applying material wrapped in game-based learning it could improve students' listening skills, the lessons became fun, easy to understand, no need again using the rote method. Here it can be concluded that applying game-based learning in learning can make lessons more interesting and fun so that students are not bored and also sleepy due to monotonous lessons. in learning, namely:

NO	NAME	Student's Statements			Reason
		Accept	Middle	Unaccepted	
1.	Zulfa Safitri			✓	It doesn't have an impact because you can't understand what you're doing and also because your abilities are still lacking.
2.	Mohammad Alfan Affandi		✓		Accepting even said that if learning is covered with media such as dabble games, learning will be very easy to understand. But feel some difficulties because the mastery of the English language is still lacking
3.	Dina Azsura Wiyanti	✓			Accept that learning is covered with dabble games because learning is fun and learning is also easy to understand.
4.	Aulia Unzila Putri	✓			Accept that learning is covered with dabble games because learning is fun and learning is also easy to understand.
5.	Dina Azsura Wiyanti	✓			Accept that learning is covered with dabble games because learning is fun and learning is also easy to understand.
6.	Devi Purnamayanti	✓			Accept that learning is covered with dabble games because learning is fun and learning is also easy to

			understand.
7.	David Sbastian Ramadhani	✓	Accepting even said that if learning is covered with media such as dabble games, learning will be very easy to understand. But feel some difficulties because the mastery of the English language is still lacking
8.	Soffan Sofyan	✓	Accepting even said that if learning is covered with media such as dabble games, learning will be very easy to understand. But feel some difficulties because the mastery of the English language is still lacking

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that out of 8 students only 1 student did not feel the impact of applying dabble games in learning English because this one student had different abilities from other students when absorbing learning. 3 other students are in the middle because their English skills are still lacking. Where they stated that learning wrapped in dabble games would be fun and easy to understand. And 4 students are very receptive to this dabble game media, because their English skills are quite good so they feel learning is more fun and learning can be easily understood

And based on observations from researchers, it turns out that by implementing Dabble games to improve listening skills in learning English, the class becomes conducive because students focus on fun and interesting learning. Not only does the class become conducive, students' interest in learning is increasing. Because basically students prefer learning wrapped in games, especially elementary school students who still love to play. And hopefully with this way students will no longer think that learning English is difficult.

Conclusion

The research entitled Dabble Game as a learning medium to improve students' listening skills. Where the object of research is grade 6 students with 6 students studied. And in this study, researchers used a qualitative approach.

Based on the research results obtained by the researchers, it can be concluded that actually using game-based learning such as Dabble Game to improve listening skills in learning English can actually improve students' English. Because without realizing it while playing they start listening, observing, looking for, and remembering the words they have to look for and arrange according to the video songs they see and listen to. All students said that with learning wrapped in this game-based learning, it was easy to understand and also fun.

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